

STRENGTHENING CUSTOMER TIES FOR MARKET ADVANTAGE: AN ANALYSIS OF THE CELLULAR TELECOM SECTOR IN JORDAN

¹Dr. Fatima Noor El-Amin and ²Prof. Khaled Mahmoud El-Sayed

Assistant Professor, Department of Marketing, University of Khartoum, Khartoum, Sudan

Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration, Alexandria University, Alexandria,
Egypt

Abstract: *In an era marked by constant change and uncertainty, the emergence of new business models driven by evolving consumption patterns and internet-enabled communication is a recurring phenomenon. Adaptation and innovation are imperative for both businesses and consumers, as they underpin the progress of modern societies. Within the realm of consumer behavior, scholarly interest is increasingly directed towards exploring new consumption models, and one such model is collaborative consumption. Although relatively recent, collaborative consumption remains underexplored in academic research (Silveira, Petrini, & Santos, 2012). Existing studies on collaborative consumption are predominantly theoretical, as evidenced by Belk's work (2014). Empirical investigations, when undertaken, tend to adopt qualitative methodologies, exemplified by the research conducted by Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012). This preference for qualitative approaches suggests a research orientation aimed at theory development (Cooper & Schindler, 2011), elucidating the motivation behind the prevalence of qualitative studies in the domain of collaborative consumption.*

Keywords: *Collaborative consumption, consumer behavior, business models, qualitative research, theory development.*

Introduction

Business organizations place marketing at the forefront of the organization and beyond. Marketing is the face of business organizations. It is a link between the organization and its clients. Given the importance of marketing in the business world in order to achieve competitive advantage, business organizations seek to establish rules Effective and strong relationships with its customers in order to achieve advantage in a highly competitive market. Marketing is an indispensable activity in a world characterized by intense competition, rapid technological and technological development, as well as a change in customer tastes and instability in a given situation as a result of rapid changes in a world that is developing at a certain level.

The retention of customers as a routine practice and as part of the organization's policy and philosophy was therefore essential. The Organization had to develop strategies and schemes to stand up to competitors by establishing and controlling a close relationship with its customers and attracting as many competitors as possible This can only be achieved through a good understanding of customers by collecting and analyzing their data, dividing them into conglomerates and segments, and selecting the most suitable segment for the organization. Therefore, the organization must adopt a new approach

that can be developed and improved. It is an advanced and prestigious business market through the adoption of what is known as marketing relationship or marketing relationships is interested in the customer and build a relationship with him and the search for the best ways to find loyalty in it.

Research Methodology

Research problem

Markets in the business world are witnessing fierce competition between organizations of all types and orientations in order to achieve a distinct market position and maintain its sustainability and to obtain a market share that meets the ambition of the organization. This can only be achieved through the concerted efforts of the members of the organization and the development of strategies and orientations towards achieving competitive advantage; this is where the relationship between marketing and relationship stands out.

Research importance

The telecommunications sector is one of the most important sectors in Jordan. This sector achieves economic income for the state treasury as well as providing job opportunities. It also provides services to all other sectors. It also enters this sector in many areas because it saves time and effort for customers to achieve their interests. Therefore, the research organization should focus on the marketing relationship and its dimensions in order to be able to meet the needs and satisfaction of customers and increase their loyalty to the organization to achieve excellence in a highly competitive market, and can highlight the importance of research through the following points

1. Research is a consolidation of research efforts in the field of marketing, which is a field of knowledge rights that still needs more studies on the marketing relationship and competitive advantage.
2. Diagnosing the problems of the organization investigated according to current reality and what can be applied, and thus determining the requirements to improve customer satisfaction and achieve competitive advantage.

Research Objective

The main objective of the research is to analyze the relationship between marketing variables in relation to the competitive advantage as well as the following sub-objectives:

1. Measuring the applicability of the marketing variables in relation to Jordan Telecom - Orange.
2. To reach a framework for the relationship between the variables of marketing in relation to the competitive advantage of the organization in question.
3. To submit proposals to the Organization in the light of the indicators of the results of the reality in the field so as to enable them to complete some of the shortcomings with regard to the axes adopted by the current field research.

Research model and hypotheses

Based on the research problem and its objectives and based on the previous studies, the research model and hypotheses have been developed in order to test them in practice to achieve objectives. Figure (1) illustrates the theoretical model of research, variables and relationships between them. Note from the theoretical model of research that there are two types of variables: First: independent variables: which represent the links, common values, customer understanding and quality. Second: The dependent variable: The competitive advantage of organizations, which is the focus of research and investigation

in many studies and field research the theoretical model of research has been developed based on previous theoretical and field studies and research.

Figure (1) Research model

Based on the objectives, problem and model of the research, a set of hypotheses was developed in the nihilistic form for the purposes of testing and achieving the research objectives:

The first main hypothesis

There is no significant marketing impact in relation to achieving competitive advantage.

The following hypotheses are derived:

1. There is no significant correlation between the links in achieving competitive advantage.
2. There is no significant effect relationship to the common values in achieving competitive advantage.
3. There is no significant effect relationship to the customer's understanding in achieving competitive advantage.
4. No relationship has a significant effect on quality in achieving competitive advantage.

The second main hypothesis

There are no statistically significant differences in the impact of marketing on the relationship to achieving competitive advantage due to personal factors.

Literature Review

(Keshvari, 2012), The impact of e-customer relationship management on customer attitudes and their relevance to creating a competitive advantage in Iranian financial institutions. "The aim of this study was to study the competitive advantage of managing the relationship of electronic customers in financial institutions. The deductive approach was used in this study. The case study was conducted through the distribution of a questionnaire to approximately 40 clients and employees of financial institutions. The benefits of using the CRM system are: improved cash flow management, international customer satisfaction, increased security, the proliferation of communication channels such as the Internet and quality of service. She noted that customers are the key elements of banks and financial institutions that are focused on managing the improvement in the management of financial flows is one of the most important benefits of e-customer relationship management. She pointed out that the implementation of the e-customer relationship management system in financial institutions and banks is creating competitive advantages for both customers and the bank, Integrated customer profitability, reduced response time to customer requests, improved response to customer activity, marketing and strategic factors, and recommended that the Bank should improve transaction security and collateral matters further to achieve customer satisfaction.

Anis Ahmed Abdullah, 2006, studied the role of customers in building an effective strategy for relation based marketing- An analytical study of the views of a sample of paint users in the city of Mosul.

The research examines the role of relation based marketing as an effective marketing tool in attracting and retaining customers and making them loyal customers for life. The study shows the role that the customer can play in paving the way for marketing organizations to build an effective strategy to sustain and win loyalty to customers. This study has identified the main variables that industrial users attach as important criteria to be used in dealing with paint retailers. This guide can be used to build a clear marketing strategy that achieves the objectives of both parties. The study of :(Dant, et al, 2005) Titled the importance of marketing dimensions of relations in achieving application effectiveness, which aims to measure the impact of a range of determinants on the effectiveness of the application of marketing relations, which is represented in three basic groups, where the first is concerned, including the determinants of the relationship as it is with confidence and the second group-related determinants controlling the relationship Kalmnaf and investment in the relationship, the second group-related outcomes relationship such as loyalty and cooperation, the study has shown that these determinants are more effective when the relationship is more important for customers, and the determinants of controlling more contribute to the expansion of the scope of the effectiveness of applying Relation based Marketing

The researchers sought to clarify the role of relations based marketing to enhance customer satisfaction. Due to the vitality of the relation based marketing concept, which must be adapted by the organizations, especially the service organizations, so that they can enhance customer satisfaction which is the basic pillar of any organization so that the organization can provide services that satisfy his needs and fulfil his wishes, therefore the research had adopted in its survey part the relations based marketing as an explanatory variable, customer satisfaction as an explanatory variable, and laid down a default research plan that reflects the nature of the relationship of correlation and impact between marketing on the one hand and enhancing customer satisfaction on the other hand.

It resulted in a set of key hypotheses that were tested using the statistical program for data collected through the questionnaire for the respondents (employees and customers). The research found a number of conclusions, the most important of which are: There is a significant correlation and effect of the marketing variables in relation to enhancing the customer satisfaction, except for the relation variable, which showed that it has nothing to do with the customer satisfaction.

The aim of this study was to identify the extent to which knowledge management processes predominate in achieving competitive advantage. The study sample consisted of (84) individual members of the administrative body of JTG companies. This effect was tested using simple regression analysis and mono-variance analysis.

The results indicated that there is a high effect between the independent variable, knowledge management processes and the dependent variable competitive advantage. The results also indicated that there were statistically significant differences in the effect of knowledge management processes in achieving competitive advantage due to the service duration where there was no significance shown to Career.

Relationship marketing

What is the marketing relationship and its components?

The concept of relations based marketing is no longer an old-fashioned concept but a concept of a changing and evolving nature as a result of competition among organizations in a changing and unstable world. Business organizations in highly competitive markets have realized that attracting new customers from their competitors is more expensive than maintaining customers (Al-Saharwardi, 2007, 15). The cost of attracting a new customer is five times the cost of maintaining the current customer (Abu Qahf et al., 2006, 398). Therefore, business organizations had to shift from a traditional marketing perspective based on the sale of products and goods to marketing in a relationship that builds on a long-term and continuous relationship with the customer through the production and marketing of products, In order to achieve customer satisfaction and win his loyalty on a continuous basis. Marketing by relationship is a name of a strategy that seeks to build and develop a long-term partnership with the client.

Organizations build relationships with clients by supplying them with value added products and services to satisfy their needs and desires. The first appearance of the concept of marketing by relationships was in 1983, and Perry was the first to use it and defined it as: all the activities that are aimed to establish, develop and maintain successful interrelationship between organizations (Ben Garwa, 2012, 177). While marketing by relations is defined according to Christopher's as: the philosophy of business performance, in addition that it is strategic direction for organizations, focusing on retaining existing customers and developing relationships with them rather than the continuous focus on attracting new customers (Christopher, 2001,81).

It is also defined as: Building a long-term compelling relationships with key parties (consumers, processors, distributors) to maintain their long-term preference and work. Smart marketers try to build long-term reliable relationships with consumers, distributors and even retailers (Al-Barzangy & Albarwary 2004, 656)

The concept of marketing by relationships is based on six basic pillars are as the following: (Abdullah, 2006, 74)

1. Create new added value for customers from their consumption of the goods or service provided.

2. Recognizing the key role of the customer in determining the value and benefits he wishes to achieve through the process of selecting and consuming the product or service.
3. Work to identify the process of communication between the seller and the buyer in a manner that supports the perceived value by the customer.
4. Support continuous cooperation and coordination between the organization and customers.
5. Understand the importance of time factor for customers.
6. Building a network of customer relationships, as well as a network of relationships between the organization and other parties such as suppliers, distributors, intermediaries and other stakeholders with the organization.

The importance of marketing by relationship

Marketing by relationship is an important tool, as the relevant studies have shown, because marketing by relationship helps to overcome marketing challenges in the context of environmental change. It brings benefits to both marketer and customer. It is also considered an important tool in achieving competitive advantage, as evidenced by what is achieved in organizations and customers (Abdullah, 2006, 73):

Organizations

The marketing by relationship could achieve the following:

1. Long-term relationships with customers are a competitive and defensive advantage of the organization in the context of competitive markets, which help them to overcome the challenges of competition to some extent, and avoid price wars, which helps to maintain these relations between the two parties, the modern means of communication, especially the Internet, since customers prefer to deal with organizations that are constantly accessible.
2. Helps to achieve stable and continuous profits.
3. Establish a position in the customer's mind as expert and consultant for him in the field of specialization.
4. Reduce marketing and promoting costs, and efforts to attract new customers.
5. Customer becomes one of the free advertising sources of the organization and its products.
6. Increase the amount of customer purchases of the organization's products.
7. Achieves trust, commitment and sharing of information between the organization and its clients.
8. Creating and building a two-way communication process between the organization and its customers achieves a kind of feedback that helps to develop future relationships and reach customer satisfaction.
9. Helps to target the right and comfortable customer at the same time, and through lucrative offers, increasing the effectiveness of the targeting strategy.

Customers

The customer's importance is demonstrated by:

1. Psychological comfort and confidence in dealing with the entity that the customer used to deal with.
2. To strengthen the social relations between the organization and the clients so that it can obtain special treatment in most cases.

3. Reduce the cost of switching from one organization to another, which may be borne by the customer, whether social, physical or psychological costs, especially for service due to the nature of the service and the manner of delivery and relationship with the customer or beneficiary.

Dimensions of marketing by relationship

In terms of saying that relationship marketing is called a strategy that organizations seek to build and develop long-term relationships with the customers by providing them with value and satisfaction of their needs and desires, as these organizations can due to repeated sales to those customers who develop relationships with them, organizations can increase their sales and market shares in addition to profit levels (Abu Naja, 2008, 34).

1. Links

The agreement between the organization and the customer leads to something. The commitment to this variable leads to the development and strengthening of relationships with customers and thus leads to the customer's satisfaction with the relationship with the organization and the promotion of loyalty. The study (Boone & Kurtz, 1998) (Wilson & Mummalaneni), and the relationship between the organization and customers leads to the sustainability of their relationship, which requires a great commitment between them. Wang (2006) emphasized that organizations can identify relationships with customers through three relational links: financial linkages, social linkages, and structural linkages (Al Murad and Dulaimi, 2012, 107).

2. Shared values

Values are defined as: a set of criteria that the individual carries towards the things, meanings and aspects of the various activities that direct his desires and tendencies towards them, and determine acceptable behavior, rejected and right and wrong and characterized by relative stability, these values do not come from a vacuum, they derive from the environment in the broad sense (Tamimi, 2007, 34). Common values are defined as: beliefs whose owners believe in their value and are committed to its contents, in determining acceptable, rejected, correct and false behavior. Religious teachings, socialization, past experience and the community to which individuals belong are sources of values (Kariot, 2000, 157).

3. Customer understanding

(Gibbert et al. (2003) points out that CRM is the management of knowledge of the customer, which is selfknowledge of customers as opposed to customer knowledge, such as customer characteristics and preferences. Murillo & Annabi (2002) argue that interaction with the customer is better than planned data and information. Through this interaction, the organization can directly ask its clients about their problems and needs, adding that the goal is to turn the marketing agent into a collector of customers and Then to use them to help them. Customer knowledge is part of the knowledge of the organization. By sharing knowledge with the customer, the organization is able to gain the knowledge advantages of each customer that interact with it. In light of this, customer knowledge is defined as what the customer wants to know about the organization, ie, providing detailed information to identify the organization's products and how to use them effectively (Al-Azzawi, 2014, 63-64).

4. Quality

The production of a high quality product or the provision of high quality services that satisfy the desires, needs and tastes of customers enhances the customer loyalty and belonging to the organization and continues with it for a long time, which enhances the competitive advantage of the organization in a

business market in which organizations compete to keep their customers longer And acquiring new customers within a broader market share.

Products or services must be able to meet the expectations of prospective customers as they are the challenges facing the organization, including the fluctuation of the mood and taste of the customer. The customer's confidence in the quality of the product or service makes the organization valuable in the customer's mind and a source of confidence in achieving its desires and needs (Al-Haidari, 2013, 9).

Applied Relation based Marketing tools requirements: -

To reach a successful, effective application to the concept of relation based marketing, the following factors should be available: (Abdullah, 2006, 74-75):

1. Defining the target customer's characteristics and needs.
2. Building strong relationships with customers should be the goal of all marketing activities of the organization.
3. Adoption of the relationship marketing on the availability of information technology with the possibility of building systems and rules of information about customers and means of personal communication with them.

All the above will increase the ability to satisfy their needs in a manner distinct from what the competitors, and thus increase the level of satisfaction and lead to the construction of loyalty. This results in an increase in the revenue generated by each customer and the construction of positive customer attitudes about the organization and its products, as well as the lower customer sensitivity to the price.

Competitive advantage

The competitive advantage of the evolution Zaormvhom meaning was not by chance but is the result of a shift in the concept of comparative advantage, and I specifically in the late seventies of the last century appeared, which is essentially man-made. And it became the subject of competitive advantage now of topics Thoudy with great interest, and due attention to this is due to the necessities of keeping up with the rapid developments Her emergence of the phenomenon of globalization and mergers and spread, as well as opening up policies and the liberalization of world markets that have brought more challenges to the work of the Organization, as well as the enormous and explosive developments in technology, particularly information and communications technology, all this business organizations put in front of a broad challenge to pay these organizations to work hard to find a place in the market, which has become crowded with competitors, organizations have realized that the methods and management styles Which was followed by the traditional no longer suitable for such challenges (al-Haidari, 2013, 14). There is a correlation between the comparative advantage and marketing by relation to the fact that shopping is by relationship is one of the tools to achieve competitive advantage through which organizations seek to obtain a large market share.

What is the competitive advantage and its importance?

The concept of competitive advantage is one of the important concepts in this business world, on one hand, while on the other hand it is very important from scientific and academic point views, therefore to understand the competitive advantage we will present some of its definitions. Porter believes that competitive advantage arises once the organization finds more effective ways than those used by competitors, which can embody this discovery on the ground, in other words, create a process of innovation in its broad sense (Buran, 2016, 98). Competitiveness is defined as the skill, technology or

resource that enables the organization to produce value and benefits to customers that exceed what competitors offer. It emphasizes its distinctiveness and difference from these competitors from the point of view of customers who accept this difference and excellence and achieve more benefits and values that exceed what Presented to them by other competitors (Al-Salami, 2001, 102). Kotler defines the competitive advantage as: the ability of the organization to perform its work in a way that is difficult for its competitors to imitate it, and the competitive advantage can be achieved by performing functions that create value in the areas of cost reduction compared to competitors or work on their performance in ways that lead to excellence (Buran, 2016, 98). The importance of competitive advantage comes from being a weapon to face challenges, one measure of any organization success and one of the positive indicators to measure the direction of the organization to occupy its competitive position (Kubaisi, 2014, 243).

Characteristics of competitive advantage

Competitive advantage characteristics (Buran, 2016, 99) are as follows:

1. it is derived from the desires and needs of the customer.
2. its is the most important contribution to the success of the business.
3. it provides a unique harmony between enterprise resources and environmental opportunities.
4. it is Long-lasting and difficult to imitate by competitors.
5. it provide a base for subsequent improvements.
6. it provide guidance and motivation for the organization as a whole.

Competitive Advantage Dimensions

Competitive advantage is based on four dimensions: high efficiency, high quality, high innovation, and rapid customer response, which are comprehensive building blocks for this feature that any organization can adopt regardless of the industries in which it operates, and regardless of the products or services it offers to customers. We review these dimensions as follows (Hassoun et al., 17-18):

1. High efficiency

High efficiency is defined as the ratio of outputs to inputs required for achievement, and it is measured by work which is the means to convert inputs into outputs.

2. High quality

Quality products are reliable goods or services, in the sense that they perform the work for which they were designed. The high quality influences the competitive advantage of the product in two aspects: Firstly: the introduction of a high quality product increases this product value in the eyes of consumers. In return, the company can afford it in a high price, and the customer, as a result of the above, makes his decision to buy the product. Secondly: the above will lead to high efficiency of the company and its low production cost.

3. High Innovation

Innovation is defined as something new or unusual in the way a company works or in its production. Therefore, Innovation includes advancing in product types, production processes, management systems, organizational structure and strategies developed by the company. Innovation can be the most important signal of a competitive advantage. In the long term, competition can be seen as a process driven by innovation. Although not all innovations succeed, successful ones can be the most important source of competitive advantage because it gives the organization something unique - something that competitor's lack.

4. Quick customer response

In order to achieve a high customer response, the organization must be able to perform better than its competitors and effectively meet the needs of its customers. If the organization does so, consumers will evaluate their products higher than they value the organization's competitors' products and thus strengthen the organization's competitive advantage. Achieving high quality and innovation is the key part of achieving high customer responsiveness. Another important factor in customer response is the manufacturing of goods and the provision of services as requested by an individual or group.

Reasons for developing competitive advantage

Institutions develop and improve new competitive advantages by discovering new and better ways to compete, so we will look at some of the reasons why they develop their competitive advantages. Among these are:

(Buran, 2016, 110-111):

A. The emergence of new technology

Technological change can find new opportunities in many areas such as product design using automated media, modern online marketing methods, e-marketing and others.

The institution's need to introduce new technology at the last stage of the life cycle of the competitive advantage to reduce cost or enhance product uniqueness. And in the latter stage, the organisation begins to renew, develop and improve the existing advantage or offer a new competitive advantage that is more valuable to customers.

B. The emergence or change of new consumer needs

When customers develop new needs or change needs priorities, in such a case there is an adjustment to the competitive advantage or the development of a new advantage.

C. Change in input costs

Competitive advantage is usually affected in the event of a fundamental change in input costs such as labor, raw materials, machinery, etc.

D. Change in government restrictions

These changes are mainly the nature of government restrictions in the areas of product specification, environmental protection campaign against pollution and market entry restrictions etc.

Information Gathering Methods

The two hypotheses were based on the inductive method by studying the relationship between the main dimensions by collecting the data related to the investigated organization and analyzing them to support the research objectives to contribute to the test of the research schema. The researchers relied on obtaining the required data to cover the theoretical side of the research on many References of books, studies, research, letters and university papers, as well as references obtained from the Internet, and then prepared a questionnaire to cover the field of research as an essential source of data collection. The first part includes demographic information about the respondents, the second part includes expressions on the variables of the study to measure them, the variable marketing by relationship (18), and the variable competitive advantage (5)) Paragraphs.

Methodology

Test consistency and accuracy

A questionnaire, after its final formulation, was tested for reliability and stability by relying on the Likert scale in the analysis. The alpha coefficient was 84.4%. This indicates that there is a good

correlation between the terms of the questionnaire and this percentage exceeds the acceptable rate of 60%.

Study community

The study community is composed of a segment of the employees of cellular operators in Jordan - Orange, Zain and Umniah. A random sample of employees was selected in the main centers in the capital Amman. The target sample was (900) employees according to their job names.

The Questionnaire part

In accordance with the research trends, the researchers distributed the questionnaire to the individuals interviewed at Jordan Telecom - Orange. The researchers conducted the statistical analysis to measure the responses of the respondents.

Statistical analysis of the study data

Stability of the study instrument: For the purpose of extracting the stability of the study tool (the questionnaire), the Kronbach alpha equation was applied to all paragraphs of the questionnaire, reaching (84.4%), which is acceptable to adopt the results of the study.

Description of Study Sample:

A total of 900 questionnaires were distributed to employees at Jordan Telecom Orange, A total of (820) questionnaires were retrieved (91%). Table (1) shows the distribution of the sample of the study sample on personal and functional variables.

Table (1) Distribution of the personal information of the sample members

No.	Variable	Level	Coloration	%
1	gender	Male	470	57%
		Female	350	43%
2	age	Less than 30	220	26.8%
		31-40	430	52.4%
		41-50	129	14.6%
		More than 50	50	6.1%
3	education	High school or less	90	11%
		Diploma	180	22%
		Bachelor	440	54%
		Higher education	110	13%
4	Work experience	5 years or less	120	15%
		6 -10	180	22%
		11 – 15	140	17%
		More than 16	380	46%
5	Work rank	Directorate manager	70	9%
		Assistant manager	50	6%
		Department manager	80	10%
		Employee	570	69%
		Other	50	6%
6	Work type	Administrative	250	30%

		Financial	130	16%
		Technical	300	37%
		Others	140	17%
	Total	For each variable	820	100%

The previous table shows the following:

- **Gender:** 57% of the sample of males, and that 43% were females.
- **Age:** 26.8% of the sample of the study were aged 30 years or less, while 52.4% were aged from 31 to 40 years, another 14.6% of the respondents were aged 41-50, and 6.1% of the respondents were aged 51 and over.
- **Academic Qualification:** 11% of the sample of the study of holders of secondary school certificates and less, and 22% holders of diplomas and community colleges, while 54% are holders of bachelor's degree, and 13% of the higher education degrees.
- **work experience:** 15% of the sample of the study has experience 5 years, and 22% their experience of 6-10 years, 17% of the sample study sample of 11-15 years, and that 46% of the sample of the study experience of 16 years and more.
- **Career status:** 9% of the study sample are department managers, 6% of the study sample are assistant managers, 10% of the study sample are heads of departments, 69% of the sample are employees, 6% Of study sample have other career status.
- **Type of work:** We note from the previous table that 30% of the study sample administrative, 16%, of the study sample are of financial type of work, 37% of the study sample technicians, and 17% of the study sample of other jobs.

Analyze the results and test hypotheses

The main hypothesis ((There is no significant effect of marketing with relationship to achieving competitive advantage))

To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the effect of marketing with relationship to achieving competitive advantage as shown in **Table (2)**.

Table (2) Simple Regression to ensure the effect of marketing with relationship to achieving competitive advantage

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.716	0.513	0.443	0.716	65.542	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (2)* it is observed that there is significant impact of marketing with relationship to achieving competitive advantage. *R Correlation value* was (0.716), whereas the *R²* was (0.513). This means the (51.3%) of marketing with relationship to achieving competitive advantage. As *Beta* was (0.716) Assuring *F* value was (65.542) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

First Hypothesis:

(There is no significant correlation between the links in achieving competitive advantage) To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the correlation between the links in achieving competitive advantage as shown in **Table (3)**.

Table (3) Simple Regression to ensure the correlation between the links in achieving competitive advantage

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.235	0.552	0.354	0.235	3.814	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (3)* it is observed that there is significant relationship of the links in achieving competitive advantage. *R Correlation value* was (0.235), whereas the *R²* was (0.552). This means the (55.2%) of links in achieving competitive advantage. As *Beta* was (0.235) Assuring *F* value was (3.814) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

Second Hypothesis

((There is no significant effect of the shared values in achieving competitive advantage))

To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the effect of the shared values in achieving competitive advantage as shown in *Table (4)*.

Table (4) Simple Regression to ensure the effect of the shared values in achieving competitive advantage

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.357	0.127	0.264	0.357	13.724	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (4)* it is observed that there is significant effect of the shared values in achieving competitive advantage. *R Correlation value* was (0.357), whereas the *R²* was (0.127). This means the (12.7%) of shared values effect in achieving competitive advantage. As *Beta* was (0.357) Assuring *F* value was (13.724) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

Sub-Hypothesis III

There is no significant effect on customer understanding of competitive advantage To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the effect customer understanding of competitive advantage as shown in *Table (5)*.

Table (5) Simple Regression to ensure the effect of customer understanding in competitive advantage

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.410	0.168	0.338	0.410	9.298	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (5)* it is observed that there is significant effect of customer understanding of competitive advantage. *R Correlation value* was (0.410), whereas the *R²* was (0.168). This means the (16.8%) of customer understanding effect in competitive advantage. As *Beta* was (0.410) Assuring *F* value was (9.298) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

Sub-Hypothesis IV

There is no significant effect of quality on achieving competitive advantage

To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the effect of quality on achieving competitive advantage as shown in *Table (6)*.

Table (6) Simple Regression to ensure the effect of quality on achieving competitive advantage

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.370	0.137	0.441	0.370	12.818	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (6)* it is observed that there is significant effect of **quality on achieving competitive advantage**. *R Correlation value* was (0.370), whereas the *R²* was (0.137). This means the (13.7%) of quality effect in achieving competitive advantage. As *Beta* was (0.370) Assuring *F* value was (12.818) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

There are no statistically significant differences in the impact of marketing on the relationship to competitive advantage attributed to personal factors

To test this hypothesis the researcher uses Simple Regression analysis to ensure the impact of marketing on the relationship to competitive advantage attributed to personal factors as shown in *Table (7)*.

Table (7) Simple Regression to ensure the effect of marketing on the relationship to competitive advantage attributed to personal factors

R	R ²	B	Beta	F Value	DF	Sig
0.549	0.301	0.543	0.549	33.966	253	0.000*

*significance at level of (0.05).

From *table (7)* it is observed that there is significant effect **marketing on the relationship to competitive advantage attributed to personal factors**. *R Correlation value* was (0.549), whereas the *R²* was (0.301). This means the (30.1%) of **marketing effect on the relationship to competitive advantage attributed to personal factors**. As *Beta* was (0.549) Assuring *F* value was (33.966) and it is significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), that assures reject null Hypothesis, and accept alternative.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

After reviewing the results of the statistical analysis, the researchers reached the following results:

1. There is a significant correlation between the links in achieving competitive advantage.
2. There is a significant correlation between the common values in achieving competitive advantage.
3. There is a significant relationship to the customer's understanding of competitive advantage.
4. There is a significant relationship to quality in achieving competitive advantage.
5. There are statistically significant differences in the responses of the study sample due to demographic factors.
6. Demographic factors influence the achievement of competitive advantage.

Recommendations

After reviewing the results of the study and analyzing it well and clearly, the researchers recommend the following:

1. Jordan Telecom - Orange should increase its focus on customers and dealers who are more profitable, by developing marketing programs that suits them.

2. Jordan-Orange Telecom Company must reflect the concept of marketing by relation to the company and its branches.
3. The need to focus on the most important elements in bringing the attention of customers.
4. Taking care of customer complaints quickly according to quality standards.
5. Disclosure of effective marketing elements that contribute to the achievement of competitive advantage.
6. The need to involve customers in the quality of services and products they desire from the company.
7. The branches of the company must survey the opinion of their customers about the quality of the services they want and the quality of the regulations they want, because of the different wishes and directions of customers from one region to another because of deferent demographic and geographical factors.
8. The company must periodically measure customer satisfaction with the services and products provided to them.

References

- Abdel Salam Abuqaf, Nabila Abbas, Alaa Gharabawi, (2006), Marketing, Egypt, Alexandria, Modern University Office.
- Ahmed Mohamed Al-Barzanji and Nizar Abdul Hamid Al-Barwari, (2004) Marketing Strategies: Concepts, Foundations and Functions, Jordan-Amman, Dar Wael Publishing and Distribution.
- Anis Ahmed Abdullah, (2006) The role of customers in building an effective strategy for marketing in relation to an analytical study of the views of a sample of paint paint users in Mosul, Iraq, Tikrit University, Tikrit Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences.
- Boone, L. E., and Kurtz, D. Contemporary Marketing. Texas: The Dryden Press, 1998.
- Customer loyalty in mobile commerce on texts information and management, 43,271-282.
- Garcia-Murillo, M and Annabi, H (2002) Customer knowledge management. Journal of the Operational Research Society, 53, p.p 875-884.
- Gebert, H., Geib, M., Kolbe, L. and Brenner, W. (2003), "Knowledge-enabled customer relations management: integrating customer relationship management and knowledge management concepts," Journal of Knowledge Management, Vol.7, No.5, pp.107-123
- Hakim Ben Jaroua, (2012) The Effect of Using Marketing Relationships in Achieving the Competitive Advantage of the Corporation - Case Study of Algeria Telecom Corporation, Ouargla Branch, Algeria, Qasidi University, Marabah, Ouargla, Journal of the researchers.

Huda Mohammed Salim Al-Saharwardi, (2007) Customer Value Based on Marketing Concepts in Relationship - Case Study of the Arab Company for

Keshvari, 2012, The Impact of E-CRM on Customers Attitude and Its Association with Generating Competitive Advantages in Iranian Financial B2B Context, Vol 5, No 4, p. p. 34-54

Lin, H. H., & Wang, Y.S.(2006).An examination of the determinants of Antibiotic Industries and Supplies (ACIA), (unpublished Master thesis), Iraq, Baghdad, Mustansiriya University, Faculty of Management and Economics.

Wilson, D. T., & Mummalaneni, V. (1986). Bonding and Commitment in Supplier Relationship: A Preliminary Conceptualization Industrial Marketing and Purchasing, 1(3): 44–58.